

**TRANSLATION ISSUES OF LITERARY TEXTS (ON THE BASIS OF
“SCORPION FROM THE ALTAR BY ABDULLAH KADIRI)**

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Annotation. This article highlights important points of translating literary texts along with main issues that arise while translating. In the first part of the article, theoretical basis of interpretation of literary texts which includes two pragmatically oriented directions. In the second part, analysis of one of the Uzbek novels that was translated into English has been provided.

Key words. Translation methods, equivalence, literary text analysis, source text.

Modern translation theory is characterized by a variety of theoretical concepts. There are a number of factors that form the subject of the general theory of translation: patterns inherent in translation in all its varieties; a system for studying its nature, essence, principles, purpose; the existence of the problem of the adequacy of the translation text to the original; identification of the historical role of translation in the development of interlingual communication of peoples, the relationship of translation with other types of spiritual activity [4;34].

Translation, as a process and result of translation activity, depends on the orientation to a certain receptor, to a typical representative of the culture of the target language. The act of translation is pragmatically oriented in two directions. Firstly, it consists in a complete reproduction of the original, and secondly, the translation is pragmatically receptor-oriented (Schweitzer, 2009; Neubetr and Shreve, 1992; Newmark, 1991; Nord, 1991; Steiner, 1975). The degree of similarity of the texts of the original and the translation to each other depends on the degree of freedom that the translator is guided by in the process of adapting the information of the source

text [5;130-137]. Studies show that even experienced translators believe that a translation that retains 80% of the original content can be considered excellent. Obviously, the higher the degree of freedom of the translator, the further the translation text is from the original, the less it reflects the content and form of the original, the more misleading the reader gets about the original [8;55].

According to L.S. Barkhudarov, the translation unit is the smallest unit of source text that has a match in the translated text. It may have a complex structure, but its parts, taken separately, are untranslatable, since no correspondence can be established with them in the translation text[9]. V.N.Komissarov believes that a translation unit is the minimum unit of speech, the presence of which in the source text is due to the appearance of a certain speech segment in the translation text[9]. D.B. Olkhovnikov argues that a separate paragraph in its linguistic, linguistic, cultural, literary or stylistic definition can be taken as a unit of translation in each specific case. He presents the structure of images in a work as a hierarchy of translation units, understanding the term “hierarchy of translation units” as carriers of content and internal form in the broad sense of the word [6;112].

The literary text covers all the genre diversity of fiction. It has two interrelated text-forming functions: impact and aesthetic. The form of presentation of the material is of great importance. The aesthetic value of the work and the level of emotionally expressive impact on the reader depend on the form in which the content of the text is reflected. In artistic texts, units and means of all styles are used, which, being included in the new system of literature, acquire a different function for themselves: aesthetic. Scientists have proposed several options for interpreting the text in translation. For example, simplification, identification of the meaning of the source text with the standard of meaning based on the past experience of the translator. Experience is the basis for the transformation of the semantic blocks of the original. Interpretation is the basic operation of hermeneutics as a science of art and interpretation of texts.

Let's consider literary translation from a literary point of view. Here literary translation is defined as "a kind of word-creative art". According to this theory, the main task of a translator is to find adequate linguistic means to reflect thoughts in words, that is, a literary translation is an adequate correspondence to the original, not so much in a linguistic sense, but rather in an aesthetic sense. This is also stated by T.A. Kazakova, saying that literary translation is "a special type of translation activity associated with the need to create texts in the process of translation that have the ability of direct aesthetic impact" [3;15].

To clarify translation difficulties, we must first highlight the universal stylistic features of a literary text. It is important to note that works of fiction are opposed to all other speech works due to the fact that for all of them the main one is one of the communicative functions, namely artistic and aesthetic or poetic.

Consequently, the main goal of any work of this type is to achieve a certain aesthetic impact, to create an artistic image. First of all, we note that a literary text always vividly reflects the characteristics of the people the writer is a representative of and the language in which he writes. Language is a reflection of the historical characteristics of the people in the perception and reflection of the surrounding world. In linguistic terms, the most striking distinguishing feature of a literary text is the extremely active use of tropes and figures of speech. The figurative reflection of the surrounding world is manifested in the presence of metaphors, comparisons, epithets, personifications, hyperbole, litotes, metonymy, etc. Tropes and figures of speech are the most powerful way to create and function a literary text. In other words, as Y.P. Solodub mentioned, "For the literary text, it is more important not what is reported, but how it is reported" [7;21].

However, while during our research, we have read some translations of Uzbek literary novels, namely, "Scorpion from the Altar" by Abdullah Kadiri. The translations of some culture-related concepts were not interpreted properly.

For example, in Uzbek, it is common to say “egasiga topshirmoq” in the meaning of “getting married” by parents of girls. Also, there is verb of “quyilmoq” taken from the expression “qarib quyilmoq” were given but not translated correctly.

In Uzbek: “Ra’noni **egasiga topshirmag‘uningizcha**, - dedi Nigor oyim, - **quyulmaydirg‘ang‘a** o‘xshaydir”

In English: I guess Rano will **not get serious** till she gets married, - said Nigoroyim.

The expression “egasiga topshirmoq” was given as “get married” which can be accepted by English readers. Nevertheless, qarib quyilmoq was rendered as getting serious which was, in my opinion, mistranslation.

Another example is the following:

In Uzbek: Solih maxdum 1230-1290-nchi hijriy yillarda “Ho‘qandi firdavsmonand”da yashag‘an bir muallim va **imom**, o‘z zamonasining istilosi bilan aytkanda “maktabdor domla”dir.

In English: Solikh Mahdum was “**teacher at school**” during 1230-1290 of Hijra. (Wrong translation, imom deb transliteration qilish kerak edi).

The word “imom” was omitted in this context and muallim was given as “teacher at school. However, we can see that in many of the translated books, the method of transliteration is used to translate the word “imom” and given as “imam” in English which is used for those who are in Islamic leadership positions.

Next example:

In Uzbek: Ko‘b ozor chekib nihoyat qorindosh-urug‘ va **mahalla** kishilarining **kengashlari** bilan o‘z uyiga maktab ochdi,

In English: He had come across many difficulties but in the end with the help of **his relatives and neighbors** he managed to open a school at his house.

The translated version of “mahalla kengashlari” was provided as “relatives and neighbours”. But the pragmatic meaning they convey are not associated with each other, therefore, the translators should have explained the concept of “mahalla”

which is a part of Uzbek culture and people who are involved in this little community.

In conclusion, the translation of a literary text is a laborious process, which includes not only the knowledge of two languages and the professional use of translation techniques. It is necessary to feel and understand the culture of another country, its mentality, moral values and ethical standards. In addition, it is important to take into account and be able to convey the hidden meanings of the work, to understand what the author wanted to convey, and what methods and means he used to achieve a certain effect and impact on the reader.

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